

Assessing Liberia's Climate Vulnerability through Statistical and Predictive Models: Trends, Drivers, and Policy Insights (1995–2035)

Hassan S. Dakowa

*Department of Environmental Science,
African Methodist Episcopal University, Monrovia, Liberia*

Abstract

Liberia has an urgent need for long-run vulnerability tracking, since many climate shocks and institutional vulnerabilities exist, threatening sustainable development and resilience planning efforts. Using national-level evidence data (1995 to 2023) acquired from ND-GAIN, this study used Pearson correlation, PCA, stepwise regression with robust standard errors, ARIMA and ETS models, and structural break detection to analyze temporal dependencies of climate vulnerability in Liberia. The results show Sensitivity and Health as main predictors, associated with household fragility, which is consistent with ecosystems and public health threat exposure, and Capacity and Infrastructure as moderate influences, which contributed to enhancing this risk factor. PCA revealed that the first two components accounted for around 86% of the variance, in agreement with the dimensional coherence of the vulnerability variable. A close-to-perfect model fit reflected the composite nature of the vulnerability index in the stepwise regression. At the same time, the forecast projected a slight increase, followed by a plateauing trend through 2035. Structural break analysis identified inflection points aligning with the transitioning of governance and changing economy. Overall, the findings highlight the need to strengthen institutional capacity, climate-proof critical infrastructure, and enhance ecosystem and health-system resilience, in alignment with Liberia's NAP (2020), NDC 3.0 (2025), and related national policy frameworks.

Keywords: *Adaptive capacity, climate vulnerability, ecosystems, health resilience, infrastructure, sensitivity.*

Suggested citation: Dakowa, H.S. (2026). Assessing Liberia's Climate Vulnerability through Statistical and Predictive Models: Trends, Drivers, and Policy Insights (1995–2035). *European Journal of Innovative Studies and Sustainability*, 2(1), 93-105. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejiss.2026.2\(1\).05](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejiss.2026.2(1).05)

Introduction

Climate change remains an acute global challenge, modifying hydrological cycles, affecting biophysical systems, and heightening socioeconomic vulnerabilities. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2021, 2023), human-induced warming, currently estimated at approximately 1.1°C above pre-industrial levels, has increased both the frequency and the intensity of extreme weather events, including heatwaves, droughts, and floods. IPCC (2023) defines vulnerability as the combined outcome of exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity, which highlights the need to develop empirical and quantitative tools for comprehensive risk assessment. Such vulnerability metrics are vital for monitoring the progress of global adaptation and in orienting national planning. Statistical and predictive modelling approaches, such as time-series analysis, regression, among others, have increasingly become key to the identification of long-run vulnerability trajectories and contribute to evidence-based policymaking regarding adaptation for developing nations.

West Africa is considered one of the most climate-sensitive regions in the world by virtue of its heavy dependence on climate-exposed sectors such as agriculture, forestry, and fisheries, and its underdeveloped institutional capacity for dealing with climate variability and climate shocks. Trends in rainfall variability, changing surface temperature, and increases in frequency of floods and droughts further compromise food security and human livelihoods in the region (Hounkpè et al., 2022). Moreover, recent research shows that drought frequency and intensity are increasing, and together with it, a vicious circle of increasing water insecurity and declining agricultural productivity (Henchiri et al., 2024). Although the dialogue on climate adaptation is growing in a big way, individual and region-level measures of vulnerability continue to be limited by the fragmented nature of available data and the lack of a unified monitoring system. Progress in statistical and hydrological modelling, spatial calibration, and multivariate methods has been seen in order to help advance a more accurate prediction of hydrological and climatic mechanisms throughout the sub-region (Dembélé et al., 2020). Furthermore, western African coastal regions, including Liberia, and the Gulf of Guinea, are exposed to greater risk from rising sea levels, acidification of oceans, and loss of biodiversity (Chukwuka et al., 2023). Together, these insights highlight the importance of integrated, analytical vulnerability assessment frameworks that balance environmental and socioeconomic domains.

Liberia exhibits a holistic nature of climate vulnerability in the region. Its economy is primarily driven by climate-sensitive sectors that support a significant portion of the population, agriculture and forestry, with a growing scale of extractive industries. The country's tropical forests face both human and natural impacts, while the coastal landscapes are increasingly vulnerable to sea-level rise, coastal erosion, and seasonal flooding. Meanwhile, inland communities deal with unpredictable rainfall and temperature fluctuations. Recent research emphasizes the specific burden of deforestation and climatic stress on Liberia's biodiversity, specifically the Upper Guinean rainforest (Gweh et al., 2025). With the awareness of the latter, the Government of Liberia, through the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), has promoted the development efforts aimed at implementing significant frameworks such as the National Adaptation Plan (NAP-2020) and the Updated Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC 3.0-2025), to develop national response, adaptation strategy, resilience measures, and capacity building towards sustainable development. However, Liberia currently has limited quantitative studies that account for the evolution of vulnerability empirically. The majority of national research is descriptive and narrow in scope, providing inadequate empirical evidence for enabling strong, data-driven climate governance.

Fragmented data and methodological limitations impede the current climate vulnerability research in Liberia and the wider sub-region. Current research also frequently adopts a cross-sectional or sector-specific design, like energy or agriculture, disregarding the interconnections among climatic, socioeconomic, and institutional drivers (Ihejirika et al., 2024). Although research advancements in modelling developments like Principal Component Analysis (PCA), multiple regression, and predictive time-series modelling have been found to be effective for regional vulnerability assessment, they have not been systematically applied to developing countries (Henchiri et al., 2024; Hounkpè et al., 2022), including Liberia. To help fill this analytical gap, this study uses multivariate statistical and predictive methods in formulating a national-scale vulnerability model for the 1995–2023 period. Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) and Exponential Smoothing (ETS) model forecasts to 2035 help to identify forward-looking trends on vulnerability trajectories in Liberia. Through combining climatic, socioeconomic, and institutional indicators, this study delivers a comprehensive empirical underpinning for adaptive policymaking.

This study aims to analyze Liberia's climate vulnerability trends and determinants for nearly three decades (1995-2023) and project future trends to 2035. Specifically, the objectives include examining the temporal trends of Liberia's composite climate vulnerability index from 1995 to 2023; identifying the main climatic and socioeconomic factors using correlation analysis, PCA, and regression models; forecasting future vulnerability levels up to 2035 with ARIMA and ETS models; and to detect significant shifts in national climate vulnerability over time.

This study provides an essential addition to Liberia's evidence-based planning for adaptation, which incorporates statistical and predictive methods for measuring long-term vulnerability. It also offers strategic implications for the EPA of Liberia and related line ministries towards the realization of the NAP (2020–2030), the NDC 3.0, among others, especially for prioritizing adaptation activities and the appropriate utilization of resources. Outside of national application, it further contributes to the regional climate science by offering examples of statistical modeling to evaluate vulnerability dynamics in data-deficient settings like Liberia. Additionally, in terms of aligning scientific knowledge with policy priorities, the research offers support for Liberia's shift from focusing on qualitative assessments to a data-driven approach to climate governance, thereby strengthening national resilience and aligning with the goals of the Paris Agreement and the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals. Academically, it will add to existing knowledge for research institutions and will serve as a reference point for students in Liberia and beyond.

Materials and Methods

Data Source and Description

This study used national-level climate vulnerability indicators from the Notre Dame Global Adaptation Initiative (ND-GAIN) database, an open-source database licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported (ND-GAIN, 2025). It covers the 1995–2023 period and offers annual composite indices reflecting Liberia's sensitivity, exposure, and adaptive-capacity climate vulnerability dimensions. The dependent variables that were included in the analysis are Capacity, Ecosystems, Exposure, Food, Habitat, Health, Infrastructure, Sensitivity, and Water, along with the composite Vulnerability index. The indicators point toward a dimension of national resilience for every single component.

For operational definitions, Capacity is defined as institutional readiness and socio-economic capacity towards preparedness and the capability to sense and to respond to climate stress, while Sensitivity refers to how vulnerable sectors are to climate disturbances. Infrastructure measures the strength of vital physical and service systems, and Health indicates the efficacy and maintenance capability of the national health system. Ecosystems and habitats demonstrate the health and functioning of ecological systems, whereas Food is the measure of food system availability, attainability, and accessibility, and Water is that of the adequacy and management of freshwater resources.

All the data were downloaded from ND-GAIN in the form of a comma-separated (CSV) format and analyzed using R for statistical consistency. The data were imported, properly sorted, and stored in chronological order: year variables fixed in integer form and indicators normalized as 0–1 to allow for comparison between variables and time. Variation of the overall vulnerability (Δ Vulnerability) was assumed as the first difference in the composite index of a given year to examine the short-run effect and is presented to reflect year-to-year variation, but is not used in further modeling. As a result, the Exposure indicator is found to have zero variance in all years (constant value = 0.4881709). Constant variables offer no statistical information, so Exposure was kept purely for descriptiveness's sake and excluded from correlation, principal-component, and regression analyses to avoid singularity and estimation bias. All the other indicators were free from zero variance, making them included in the multivariate analysis.

The Analytical Technique and Framework

As illustrated in Figure 1, the process of analysis was a sequential quantitative workflow undertaken to identify the key climate vulnerability drivers of Liberia and its respective temporal dynamics. The approach was structured as six integrated steps of descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, multivariate modelling, and forecasting. Because the ND-GAIN Vulnerability score is constructed from these same components, the following analysis should be interpreted as an examination of the internal structure of the index rather than the identification of external causal drivers.

Initially, the descriptive statistics were calculated to provide a summary of the distribution, central tendency, and variability for all the indicators of vulnerability from 1995 to 2023. This served to define the overall range and stability of each variable and facilitated the detection of outliers or near-constant series before model fitting. The mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum were computed for each indicator to measure how the data behaved and to provide insight for further analyses.

Thereafter, linear correlations among the chosen vulnerability indicators: Capacity, Infrastructure, Food, Health, Sensitivity, Water, and Ecosystems were estimated using pairwise Pearson correlation coefficients. Variables were standardized beforehand (z-scores) to allow for comparability before analysis. Significance was tested for the correlation at a 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$). The correlation values were arranged by absolute magnitude ($|r|$) to indicate the strongest positive and negative correlations with the composite Vulnerability Index. The resulting matrix was a preliminary indication of variable interdependence, which informed the subsequent principal-component analysis.

Subsequently, the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed to minimize multicollinearity and to reveal latent dimensions reflecting the structure of climate-vulnerability in Liberia. Eight standardized predictors were included, excluding Exposure for its zero variance. All variables were normalized using z-scores before analyses, which helped to maintain comparability between scales. Component retention was done according to the Kaiser criterion (eigenvalues > 1), and the scree plot was inspected for possible dimensional adequacy. Dominant thematic groupings were interpreted with variable loadings greater than $|0.50|$. The first two components were subsequently examined to capture institutional, infrastructural, and ecological dimensions supporting national vulnerability.

Furthermore, the stepwise multiple-regression analysis was used for the selection of the most important predictors of the composite climate-vulnerability index in Liberia. The model selection followed the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) to achieve a trade-off between explanatory power and parsimony in variables by adding and removing predictors from the model in an iterative fashion. All variables retained from the PCA stage were entered as candidate variables. Diagnostic tests were conducted before modeling in order to verify linearity, independence, and homoscedasticity assumptions. Multicollinearity was estimated by Variance Inflation Factors (VIFs), and residual normality and autocorrelation were examined using the Shapiro–Wilk and Breusch–Godfrey tests, respectively. Redundancy of predictors with high VIF (> 10) was assessed. The final model contained only statistically significant variables ($p < 0.05$) and generated standardized beta coefficients, showing the relative influence of each feature on national vulnerability.

In order to predict Liberia's national climate vulnerability through 2035, two time-series models were used: the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) and the Exponential Smoothing (ETS) were applied to historical vulnerability index data from 1995–2023. Both models were trained and validated using a rolling-origin cross-validation framework that provided one-step-ahead forecasts to measure prediction accuracy. Four statistical indicators were used to measure model performance: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), AIC, and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). Finally, the model with the lowest prediction error and most parsimonious structure was selected for final forecasting.

Finally, year-to-year first differences (ΔV) of the national vulnerability index were computed for detecting short-term and long-term changes in Liberia's climate sensitivity. Structural change analysis was conducted via the Mann–Kendall (MK) non-parametric trend test and piecewise linear regression to identify potential time series breakpoints. A five-year rolling mean and Locally Estimated Scatterplot Smoothing (LOESS) were conducted in order to reduce noise and visualize decadal change. Statistical significance was calculated at the 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$).

These analytical techniques and steps connected assessment of historical variability to predictive modeling such that descriptive diagnostics guided subsequent time series forecasts from empirical inference to policy relevance (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Analytical Framework

Statistical and Computational Tools

For this study, the statistical analyses were performed in R version 4.5.0, an open-source environment popularly used in quantitative social, climate, and ecological studies. The analysis utilized a collection of specialized R libraries, including tidyverse (data wrangling and visualization), psych (descriptive and correlation statistics), car (regression diagnostics and multicollinearity assessment), forecast (time-series modelling), FactoMineR and factoextra (principal component analysis and visualization), lmtest (statistical inference and diagnostic testing), and sandwich (heteroscedasticity-consistent covariance estimation). This was followed by model validation and diagnostic tests for the robustness of the results. Residuals were tested for normality using the Shapiro–Wilk test, and serial autocorrelation in regression models was measured using the Breusch–Godfrey test. To identify multicollinearity, VIFs were calculated, and confirmed that correlated predictors did not influence coefficient estimates. To detect heteroscedasticity, all standard errors of the final linear regression models were adjusted using heteroscedasticity-consistent estimators (HC1) according to White’s correction protocol. Visualizations were done with ggplot2 using serif fonts and high-contrast color schemes to enhance clarity and accessibility for technical, policy, and general audience consumption. All analyses were done in a script R workspace, with describable workflows that can be made reproducible and validated in order to verify and modify for future climate-vulnerability monitoring in Liberia.

Ethical and Analytical Considerations

This research solely relied on publicly available and officially released datasets extracted from the ND-GAIN index. There was no primary data collected, and no human subjects were involved; hence, ethical clearance was not a requirement for this study. All the analyses were developed in line with the principles of academic integrity, transparency, and reproducibility. Since the study was delimited to only statistical analysis, without spatial disaggregation, it limits the ability to identify county-level heterogeneity in vulnerability. All results apply strictly at the national level; ND-GAIN does not provide county-level resolution, and sub-national implications should therefore be interpreted as hypotheses for future research. In addition, the use of composite indices may introduce measurement uncertainty associated with indicator weighting and normalization. Even with these conditions, the methodological robustness and multi-model validation of the study contribute to the reliability of its national-level insights and policy implications.

Result

This section presents the analytical results. The methods are applied for clearly differentiated purposes: the descriptive statistics provide the pattern of the dataset, while correlation assesses pairwise associations, PCA identifies the underlying dimensional structure, regression evaluates conditional relationships, and change detection was used to detect shifts and structural change in the dataset. This separation of analytical functions ensures methodological rigor and prevents redundancy in the interpretation of findings.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics for Liberia climate vulnerability indicators (1995–2023), as shown in **Table 1**, the overall vulnerability index averaged 0.56 (± 0.013), indicating moderate systemic exposure to climate risks. Institutional Capacity was consistently high and stable (mean = 0.73), indicating gradual adaptation readiness gains. Infrastructure (mean = 0.41) and Health (mean = 0.70; SD = 0.07) showed greater variability, suggesting continued structural and public-health sensitivity. Ecosystems (mean = 0.56) and Water (mean = 0.40) remained relatively steady, implying limited ecological fluctuation. Food (mean = 0.61) and Habitat (mean = 0.67) indices exhibited moderate dispersion, characteristic of sectoral responses to climatic variability. Exposure was held constant (0.4881709) with zero variation and was not included in subsequent analyses, because the component was constant throughout the period due to ND-GAIN data constraints; its exclusion reflects a limitation of the dataset rather than evidence of stable exposure conditions. The increase in vulnerability (Δ Vulnerability = 0.07 ± 0.013) is signified by gradual, rather than abrupt, interannual changes. In general, Liberia’s climate vulnerability is moderate and persistent, generally consisting of fairly resilient institutional and ecological elements but limited by weaknesses in infrastructure and health sectors.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Climate Vulnerability in Liberia

	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>
Capacity	29	0.728415977	0.020461082	0.686563501	0.748187322
Ecosystems	29	0.555111194	0.002754076	0.548199674	0.558091571
Exposure	29	0.488170926	0	0.488170926	0.488170926
Food	29	0.611210498	0.020664755	0.574223189	0.633869699
Habitat	29	0.670576971	0.007234477	0.656409088	0.685590998
Health	29	0.698924947	0.072628324	0.580697035	0.777029777
Infrastructure	29	0.408954676	0.02298435	0.358929084	0.431993224
Sensitivity	29	0.499045305	0.034232304	0.443984758	0.535883678
Water	29	0.398340578	0.000968151	0.3961024	0.399428335
Vulnerability	29	0.557186477	0.012547283	0.537843879	0.577101299
Vulnerability Δ	29	0.069840418	0.012591893	0.05242613	0.089101133

Note: *n* = Sample Size; *SD* = Standard Deviation

Correlation Analysis

The correlation matrix seen in Figure 1 displays two major clusters of common indicators. Capacity, Infrastructure, and Food are a socio-institutional cluster with relatively modest intercorrelations, and Health, Sensitivity, and Water are a more robust ecological-health cluster. Most associations were positive; Capacity ($r = 0.23$, $p = 0.30$) and Food ($r = 0.02$, $p = 0.93$) were weak and non-significant. This shows direct relations with the overall vulnerability index (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Correlation Heatmap

Additionally, analyzing the direct links to the overall Vulnerability index, Figure 2 below shows that Sensitivity ($r = 0.85, p < 0.001$) and Health ($r = 0.83, p < 0.001$) are the most significant predictors, while Infrastructure ($r = 0.48, p = 0.018$) is identified as the second most significant in Liberia’s vulnerability. Ecosystems ($r = 0.33$) and Water ($r = 0.32$) have intermediate effects. Collectively, the correlation results underline that while the capacity of institutions does not play a major role in determining climate vulnerability in Liberia, vulnerability remains largely due to sensitivity and deficits of the health system, and adaptive policies that focus on strengthening health infrastructure and social protection systems are critically needed.

Figure 3. Vulnerability Drivers Bar Plot

Principal Component Analysis

Based on PCA of Liberia’s climate vulnerability dataset, two dominant axes accounted for 85.7% of the total variance, as seen in Figure 4 below. The first component (PC1) is responsible for 60.2% of the

variance, as the highest positive loadings were noted for Food, Water, and Capacity, implying that this dimension accounts for the production/resources gradient over the data observed. Structurally, these factors reflect livelihood resilience and ecosystem productivity, suggesting that the more food and water Liberia has, the better its adaptive capacity can be. The very steep eigenvalue reduction posts the first component on the scree plot, supports the predominance of this main axis, again establishing that the underlying variability of the system is heavily dominated by dynamics between food and water in the system, and capacity.

Figure 4. PCA Scree Plot Variance Explained

As seen in **Figure 5** below, the second component (PC2), accounting for another 25.5% of the total variance, was dominated by Sensitivity, Health, and Infrastructure. This axis separates systems by virtue of their socio-infrastructure fragility, highlighting circumstances in which human health-related risks and exposure to structural variables magnify climate-related risks even as resources are abundant. Where this biplot reveals these variables' positioning in orthogonal fashion among biophysical resilience (PC1) and socio-environmental sensitivity (PC2) points towards the dual character of Liberia's vulnerability profile. In sum, the PCA findings demonstrate that strengthening food and water security together with institutional capacity (PC1) and minimizing health and infrastructure-induced sensitivities would produce the most effective interventions in promoting climate resilience across Liberia.

Figure 5. Dim 1 & 2 of PCA Variable Contribution

Stepwise Multiple Regression

Six significant predictors of Liberia's vulnerability index were identified using stepwise regression: Sensitivity, Capacity, Infrastructure, Health, Water, and Habitat (Figure 6). The model explained nearly all observed variation ($R^2 = 1.00$, $p < 0.001$), consistent with the composite structure of the index. Among the predictors, Sensitivity ($\beta = 0.31$, $p < 0.001$) and Capacity ($\beta = 0.28$, $p < 0.001$) had the greatest positive effects, indicating the major drivers of vulnerability were sectoral fragility and insufficient institutional readiness. Infrastructure ($\beta = 0.06$, $p < 0.001$), Health ($\beta = 0.03$, $p < 0.001$), and Water ($\beta = 0.03$, $p < 0.001$) had other, but far smaller effects, emphasizing the public health and infrastructure deficits as constraining adaptive capacity. Habitat showed a negative, nonsignificant coefficient ($p = 0.18$), indicating a weak direct effect once other factors were controlled. Diagnostic tests showed normally distributed residuals (Shapiro–Wilk $p = 0.48$) and homoscedasticity, while moderate autocorrelation persisted (Breusch–Godfrey $p = 0.001$). The high VIF figures for Sensitivity (350) and Health (331) reflected their conceptual overlap, but the overall model stability remained acceptable. Taken together, the regression results strengthen the correlation and PCA results: Liberia's climate vulnerability is primarily governed by sensitivity, institutional capacity, and infrastructure, with secondary contributions from health and water systems. These findings indicate strong quantitative reasons to invest in facilities that increase institutional resilience and build physical infrastructure, as well as increase access to basic services to reduce national vulnerability over time.

Figure 6. Stepwise Regression Coefficient Intervals

Climate Vulnerability Forecasting (to 2035)

The model comparison results indicated that ETS was considered a proper forecasting method, which has the lowest error statistics (RMSE = 0.0050; MAE = 0.0034). As a result, this model was retained for the final projection of Liberia's climate vulnerability. The projected values indicate a relatively stable national vulnerability trend, with a mean annual estimate of 0.538 for the 2024–2035 time frame, and narrow 80 % and 95 % prediction intervals (0.518–0.558 and 0.507–0.569, respectively). Such small boundaries indicate relatively low interannual variability in vulnerability, suggesting that the country's total vulnerability to climate risks will remain unchanged without targeted interventions (Figure 7). Consequently, the results indicate the importance of improving adaptive capacity, especially in the health and infrastructure sectors, to alter the otherwise unchanging pattern of national vulnerability.

Figure 7. Liberia’s Climate Vulnerability Forecast to 2035

Change Detection

The nationwide vulnerability pattern between 1995 and 2023 demonstrated no statistically significant monotonic trend (MK tau = 0.02, $p = 0.896$). The values observed fluctuated across a long-scale mean of circa 0.556 (as shown in Figure 8), with notable peaks between 2005 and 2010, followed by a gradual decline after 2015. The LOESS and the five-year moving-average curves showed only short-term movement, and not a fixed or time-varying trend. It showed a gradual upward curve for the piecewise linear fit until around 2010 and was in a downward trend afterwards, with neither segment in the analysis reaching statistical significance ($p > 0.05$) in both cases. The slope overall was almost zero, indicating that Liberia’s vulnerability had been, in general, stable for the last three decades. This suggests that while adaptive capacity and institutional performance, in certain periods, appeared to show occasional improvements, this was offset by subsequent dips in resilience (including health and infrastructure). It is implied that the country has plateaued in national vulnerability and that structural policies are needed to achieve some measurable short- and long-term reductions, as noted by the absence of a significant long-term trend.

Figure 8. Climate Vulnerability Trend of Change Detection

Discussion

The analytical framework utilized descriptive, structural, and temporal models to assess Liberia's climate vulnerability between 1995 and 2023. The results indicated that national vulnerability statistics were stable over the study period, with no significant long-term change. Thus, in an environment that seems relatively stable, the presence of high sensitivity and institutions that have little capacity to deal with this situation shows that vulnerability is a matter driven not by short-term variability in climate but of structural and socio-economic constraint. As is also highlighted by the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (2022), governance and institutional fragility were found to be among the central factors that keep vulnerability high in African regions.

Sensitivity, institutional capacity, and infrastructure were the greatest predictors, which revealed that sensitivity, institutional capacity, and infrastructure were the best predictors of the vulnerability among Liberia's composite vulnerability. The dominance of sensitivity underscores the persistent relationship of livelihoods to climate-sensitive industries like agriculture and fisheries, where exposure to unpredictable rainfall and drought hampers productivity and household stability. This is consistent with the Liberia Climate and Development Report (2023), which was published by the World Bank, which notes infrastructure shortfalls, limited market access, and governance shortfalls as significant obstacles to climate resilience. Weak capacity has added another constraint to integrated adaptation measures in planning for local development, an issue also addressed in the NAP for Liberia (2020–2030).

The central element of Water and Habitat reveals the ecological basis of Liberia's susceptibility. Wetlands are degraded, deforestation and water quality declines diminish the natural buffering ability of ecosystems; poor health infrastructure reduces the recovery from climate-related shocks. The State of the Environment and Outlook Report for Liberia (2021) highlights these intertwined threats underlining a global public health challenge due to loss of biodiversity and environmental degradation, and inappropriate consumption of refuse. As the FAO (2022) report on global food security similarly highlights, the environmental decline and decrease in ecosystem services strengthen the conditions of livelihood and health vulnerability in low-income countries.

The forecasting analysis showed for 2022 a stable trajectory of vulnerability to 2035, in which the average index value was 0.538 and the prediction intervals were narrow. The lack of a significant long-term trend indicates that adaptation measures haven't increased resilience but kept it steady. Such stagnation captures the adaptation financing gap and implementation constraints found in the UNEP Adaptation Gap Report (2023), which states that the majority of developing countries are underfunded, underprepared, and under-resourced for the effects of climate change. So Liberia's relatively stable but high vulnerability level can be seen as a state of equilibrium, where little adaptive progress mitigates persistent exposure and sensitivity.

Overall, the findings are very consistent with previous national assessments of Liberia (2021), and with policy frameworks like NAP (2020–2030) and NDC 3.0 (2025–2035). These instruments underscore the same priorities of policy, such as institutional reform, infrastructure development, and capacity building, as preconditions for reducing vulnerability. Combining multivariate data with forecasting and trend prediction, this study adds qualitative insights into a quantitative model that connects vulnerability drivers to future predictions. This data adds to the empirical foundations of climate planning and policy coherence within national adaptation programs.

The continued existence of high sensitivity and low institutional capacity highlights the necessity for structural rather than piecemeal approaches to adaptation. Good governance, better fiscal decentralization, and targeted investment in health, water, and infrastructure systems will be key to reducing vulnerability. Integrating climate-related considerations into development planning and budget frameworks is essential for long-term resilience, as discussed in the World Bank (2023) and IPCC (2022). As NAP and NDC 3.0 implementation in Liberia continues, the process of embedding quantitative vulnerability monitoring (quantitative measures) into the approach is important for ensuring that

adaptation policies are evidence-based, measurable, and underpinned by national and international climate priorities.

Although the assessment framework does serve to describe overall trends at the national level, it does not take into account geographical and socio-political differences affecting vulnerability across counties. Finally, future work should integrate geospatial and participatory information from county environmental committees, as a recommendation to consider in the EPA (2021) publication. Extending the framework to incorporate social and economic scenarios as well as climate projections would allow more of a precise forecast beyond 2035 and would improve its usefulness for subnational planning.

Conclusion

This study utilized a robust quantitative framework to examine Liberia's climate vulnerability from 1995 through 2023 and to forecast its trajectory through 2035. The findings reveal a statistically steady state of national vulnerability, which conceals persistent structural fragilities in certain sectors. Sensitivity, institutional capacity, and infrastructure are the main drivers of vulnerability; ecological and health systems have auxiliary, but reinforcing, effects. These results suggest that the vulnerability of Liberia is defined more by governance and institutional conditions, rather than by short-term climatic variability, in line with recent research conducted by the IPCC (2022) and World Bank (2023) for sub-Saharan Africa. The lasting sensitivity demonstrates limited incremental adaptation and underscores the requirement for systemic shifts to improve coordination, funding, and rollout of resilience interventions. This study presents empirical evidence supporting the argument for a country's context sustainable policy approach to lower a nation's vulnerability. Reformers through renormalization of institutional governance, fiscal devolution, and investment for infrastructure, water, and health systems, are key for enduring resilience. Such alignment of priorities with the NAP and NDC 3.0 will assure a clear data-driven pathway toward national adaptation. Bridging the adaptation finance gap identified by UNEP (2023) and addressing the socio-ecological linkages underscored by FAO (2022) will enable Liberia to even further improve climate risk management.

Hence, the Government of Liberia should emphasize institutional reforms and adaptive governance mechanisms as the root of national resilience building based on these findings. Investments should be devoted to building climate-resilient infrastructure, decentralized water and health systems, and early-warning and monitoring systems. Incorporating climate-risk indicators into national development planning by strengthening the EPA's coordination mandate will build accountability and policy coherence. In addition, developing coalitions and cross-sectoral partnerships between development agencies, private actors, and research institutions is required to overcome the adaptation finance shortfalls and integrate data-informed decision-making. Collectively, they create a credible pathway for Liberia to institutionalize resilience and prevent rising climate risks from affecting socio-economic systems alike.

Reference

- Chukwuka, A. V., Omogbemi, E. D., & Adeogun, A. O. (2024). Habitat sensitivity in the West African coastal area: inferences and implications for regional adaptations to climate change and ocean acidification. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 196(1), 79. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-023-12171-z>
- Dembélé, M., Zwart, S., Ceperley, N., Mariéthoz, G., & Schaepli, B. (2020). *Multivariate and spatially calibrated hydrological model for assessing climate change impacts on hydrological processes in West Africa* (No. EGU2020-9143). Copernicus Meetings. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu2020-9143>

- FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP, and WHO. 2022. *The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2022. Repurposing food and agricultural policies to make healthy diets more affordable*. Rome, FAO. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc0639en>
- Gweh, A., Bailey, A., Palmeirim, A. F., Poultonor, J., Toe, H., Crowley, W., ... & Prist, P. R. (2025). Medium-sized and large bodied mammals of Marshall Wetlands, a proposed protected area in Liberia. *Check List*, 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.15560/21.1.1>
- Henchiri, M., Zhang, J., Li, S., Essifi, B., & Wilson, K. (2024). Comprehensive assessment of drought vulnerability and resilience over North and West Africa during 1980–2100. *Agricultural Water Management*, 296, 108804. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2024.108804>
- Houngpè, J., Badou, D. F., Ahouansou, D. M., Totin, E., & Sintondji, L. O. (2022). Assessing observed and projected flood vulnerability under climate change using multi-modeling statistical approaches in the Ouémé River Basin, Benin (West Africa). *Regional Environmental Change*, 22(4), 112. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-022-01957-5>
- Ihejirika, P., Nteegah, A., & Nwaozuzu, C. (2024). Do Energy Access and Climate Change Worsen Poverty in West Africa? Empirical Evidence using Panel Analysis. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*, 07(06). <https://doi.org/10.47191/jefms/v7-i6-29>
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). (2021). *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press.
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). (2023). *AR6 Synthesis Report: Climate Change 2023*. Geneva: IPCC.
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). *Climate Change 2022 – Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability: Working Group II Contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press; 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009325844>
- Notre Dame Global Adaptation Initiative. (2025, June). *ND-GAIN Country Index Dataset*. University of Notre Dame [Review of ND-GAIN Country Index Dataset. University of Notre Dame]. University of Notre Dame. <https://gain-new.crc.nd.edu/about/download?utm>
- UN Environment Programme. (2023, November 2). *Adaptation Gap Report 2023*. UNEP - UN Environment Programme. <https://www.unep.org/resources/adaptation-gap-report-2023>
- World Bank. (2023). *The climate change and conflict nexus in West Africa: A new approach for operationally relevant vulnerability assessments*. Washington, DC: The World Bank.